

The nexus of corruption and non-performing loan: machine learning approach

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ABSTRACT

Banking institutions around the world are facing a serious problem with non-performing loans (NPLs), which can jeopardize their financial stability and hinder their ability to issue new loans. The issue of NPLs has been linked to corruption, which has emerged as one of the contributing factors. Given the scarcity of research on the use of machine learning (ML) techniques to examine the relationship between corruption and NPLs, this paper provides an empirical evaluation of various ML algorithms for predicting NPLs. Besides ML performance comparisons, this paper presents the analysis of ML features importance to justify the effect of corruption factor in the different ML algorithms for predicting NPLs. The results indicated that most of the tested ML algorithms present good ability in the prediction models at accuracy percentages above 70% but corruption index has contributed very minimal effect to the ML performances. The most outperformed ML algorithm in the different proposed settings is random forest. The framework of this research is highly reproducible to be extended with a more in-depth analysis, particularly on problems of NPL as well as on the ML algorithms.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Non-performing loans (NPLs) have posed a substantial challenge for banks across the world [1]. According to Orlando and Pelosi [2], NPLs are the loans that have either defaulted or are on the brink of default, indicating that the borrower may not repay the loan according to its initial terms. Previous research has shown that a number of macroeconomic factors, including as the global financial crisis [3], [4], the COVID-19 pandemic [5], as well as unemployment and inflation rates [3], [6]–[9], contribute to NPLs. Recently, some academics [10]–[12] have emphasized the effect that corruption has on NPLs. Desta [13] defined corruption as an unethical or illegal use of power for personal gain, often involving practices like embezzlement, fraud, bribery, and nepotism [13]. It erodes public trust in government, public and private institutions [14] and can result in negative outcomes for individuals and society, such as reduced economic growth and social inequality.

The banking sector, in particular, is vulnerable to corruption which eventually erodes the public's confidence in the financial system. It's because corruption leads to an unfair distribution of opportunities and resources, particularly during the credit allocation process, which raises the risk of loan default and increases the amount of NPLs. Indeed, Son *et al.* [15] contend that corruption in the allocation of credit can lead to loans

being given to borrowers who are not qualified or deserving of them because corrupt bank employees or officials may take part in or overlook dishonest loan practices like falsifying loan documents, or insider trading.

The NPLs have a major and detrimental impact on bank performance in a number of ways, including decreased bank profitability, capital, and lending capacity [16]. It's because having a lot of NPLs can result in larger loan loss provisions, which can lower a bank's net revenue and profitability. This situation will also result in a decline in the bank's capacity to make new loans as the bank may need to set aside more capital to cover loan losses. As a result, the bank's reputation will suffer, which will lower confidence among shareholders, staff, and customers. In Malaysia, NPLs have been a substantial issue for the banking sector. The NPL ratio in Malaysia has been gradually increasing since the late 1990s, with some fluctuations [17]. At the same time, the country continues to have difficulty combating corruption on all levels. Malaysia was rated 61st out of 180 nations in the 2021 corruption perception index (CPI), with a score of 52 out of 100 [18], despite the government's efforts to combat corruption in the nation. The CPI index measures the public's opinion of official corruption in a given country. The lower the CPI score, the greater the public view of the chance of Malaysian officials being involved in corruption.

Thus, it is becoming crucial for banking institutions, stakeholders, and regulators to anticipate NPLs with corruption. Machine learning (ML) has recently emerged as a critical predictive mechanism in a number of fields, including in education [19], [20], fraud detection [21] and medical [22]. Also, a number of studies [23]–[25] have demonstrated that ML can produce findings that are more accurate when predicting NPLs. For instance, Bellotti *et al.* [23] uses a private database from a European debt collection firm to compare the results of a diverse range of regression approaches and ML algorithms for forecasting recovery rates on non-performing loans. The results show that rule-based algorithms such as cubist, boosted trees and random forests perform significantly better than other approaches. Meanwhile, Serengil *et al.* [24] apply various ML algorithms to develop NPL prediction models on a customer portfolio dataset in a private bank in Turkey. Using a large dataset, 181,276 samples, different performance metrics; precision, recall, F1 score, imbalance accuracy (IAM), specificity has been performed. The findings reveal that light gradient boosting machine (LightGBM) gave the best results among the logistic regression, support vector machine (SVM), random forest (RF), bagging classifier, eXtreme gradient boosting (XGBoost) and long short-term memory (LSTM) for the dataset.

Moreover, Elnaggar *et al.* [25] used an Egyptian credit dataset with 112,907 occurrences and 17 characteristics to predict non-performing loans. For training and testing purposes on the dataset, classification techniques such as logistics regression (LR), k-nearest neighbors (KNN), SVM, decision tree (DT), and meta-classifier have been used in this study. The findings demonstrate that the ensemble method's accuracy outperforms all others.

Notwithstanding the widespread use of ML in NPLs, the inclusion of corruption is extremely scarce in the literature. Recent studies on corruption-NPLs mostly relied on conventional essential approaches mainly multiple linear regression [10]–[12]. Therefore, the objective of this study is to extend the state-of-the-art of corruption by focusing on ML NPLs prediction models. The existence of advanced techniques of ML can be deployed immensely and to start with a few of them is highly crucial. Besides identifying the ML performances through prediction accuracy and time efficiency, another important question that needs to be answered is how the corruption aspect contributed to the performances of different ML models. This issue has not been broadly discussed in the existing research reports.

2. METHOD

2.1. Sample of data

This study uses 351 of bank year observations listed on the Malaysian stock exchange as a sample dataset. Similar to prior research [11]–[13], this study uses a corruption index to measure corruption. Particularly, this study uses the following formula to measure the degree of annual corruption of the country: $CI = 100 - CI$ index scores by transparency international. There are 10 features that derived from two main categories; bank specific characteristics (bank size (size), bank liquidity (liquidity), management efficiency (MEf), bank profitability (ROAA and ROAE)), credit risk and Islamic banking status and macroeconomics (corruption (CI), gross domestic product growth rate (GDPG) and annual inflation rate (INF)). The dependent variable is NPL that is defined as impaired loans to gross loans ratio. The correlation coefficient from Pearson correlation test of each feature to the dependent variable was identified as listed in Table 1. Corruption index has the highest correlation, which is expected as the most important feature importance in the ML prediction models for predicting the NPL.

Table 1. Features weights of correlations to NPL

Features/Variables	Meaning	Measurement method	Correlation
Corruption index	Corruption index is the perceived levels of public-sector corruption in a country	CI=100-CI index scores by transparency international.	0.464
GDPG	GDP growth rate	GDP growth rate.	0.004
INF	Annual inflation rate	Inflation rate.	0.203
ROAA	Return on average assets	ROAA is defined as net income over the average assets.	0.177
ROAE	Return on equity	ROAE is defined as net income over the average equity.	0.157
Size	Bank size	The bank size is defined as the logarithm of total assets.	0.231
Liquidity	Liquidity ratio	The liquidity ratio equals the loan divided by customer's deposits.	0.208
MEf	MEf	MEf is measured by dividing the operating expenses by the operating income generated, signaling bank efficiency in managing their operation by reducing costs and increasing profit.	0.200
IB	Classification of Islamic bank and non-Islamic bank	Islamic banks are assigned as 1, while others equal to 0.	0.079
CR	Credit risk	CR is defined as the ratio of doubtful debts to total loans.	0.456

2.2. The machine learning algorithms

Based on auto model RapidMiner preliminary study, four out of six suggested ML algorithms were selected to be compared namely DT, random forest, gradient booster and SVM. The rest of two algorithms namely generalized linear model and deep learning performed less than these four algorithms at mean absolute error (MAE) above 0.4 and relative error above 50%. All the four algorithms have a few hyper-parameters, which are optimized by the auto model RapidMiner. Figure 1 shows that the best maximal depth for DT was 4 to achieve and the lowest relative error rate can be achieved is 43.5%. Furthermore, for random forest (refer Figure 2), the best error rate was 41.2% with maximal depth 7, number of trees 100. The lowest error for gradient boosted trees was 42.8 with setting in Figure 3 while for SVM was 41.8%, which depicted in Figure 4. The hyper-parameters settings were used by researchers to develop manual ML models in RapidMiner to observe the performances based on different split ratios.

Error Rates for Parameters

Figure 1. The best configuration for decision tree

Error Rates for Parameters

Figure 2. The best configuration for random forest

Figure 3. The best configuration for gradient boosted trees

Figure 4. The best configuration for SVM

2.3. Training approach and evaluation techniques

Separating the collected dataset into training and testing is an important step for evaluating the ML algorithms. From the 351 records, 211 were used for training and the rest 140 were used as the hold-out samples for testing the ML prediction ability. Thus, the split ratio between training and testing was 60:40. Root mean square error (RMSE) and MAE were used to measure the model accuracy while R squared (R^2) can be used as an additional metric to indicate the total features importance in the NPL prediction models.

Based on the preliminary findings from auto model RapidMiner, manual processes were developed as depicted in Figure 5. The process begins with reading the NPL dataset, identifying the role (DV), split data according to different groups of split ratios (60:40, 70:30, 80:20), training the ML algorithms, testing (apply model), and comparing the performances.

Figure 5. Developing machine learning models in RapidMiner

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results were divided into two. Firstly, the results of the performances of the ML in predicting NPL are given in Table 2. Secondly, how important is the corruption index in comparison with other features in each of the ML algorithms will be presented.

Regardless of ML algorithms, the results in Table 3 show a significant performance improvement from the split ratio 60:40 to 70:30 but consistent achievement at 80:20. Slight improvement by SVM from split ratio 70:30 to 80:20. The most outstanding ML algorithm is random forest with the highest R^2 and lowest RMSE and MAE at all the split ratios. Considered split ratio 70:30 as the best setting for most of the algorithms, this setting was chosen to be furtherly compared in accordance to the features importance as given in Table 3. In Table 3 present the most feature importance is MEF for DT, random forest, and gradient boosted trees. The corruption index is the most important feature only in SVM. Some features have no correlation coefficient weights to the NPL namely IB in random forest, ROAE, and CR in SVM.

Table 2. The performance results

Algorithm	R^2	RMSE	MAE
Split ratio 80:20			
Decision tree	0.72	3.43	3.29
Random forest	0.77	3.26	2.55
Gradient boosted tree	0.65	4.31	3.01
Support vector machine	0.75	4.21	2.55
Split ratio 70:30			
Decision tree	0.72	3.43	3.29
Random forest	0.77	3.28	2.57
Gradient boosted tree	0.65	4.37	3.01
Support vector machine	0.73	4.33	2.75
Split ratio 60:40			
Decision tree	0.70	4.86	3.48
Random forest	0.77	3.46	2.61
Gradient boosted tree	0.64	4.77	3.12
Support vector machine	0.70	4.64	2.88

Table 3. The weights of correlations of each NPL feature

Feature	Decision tree	Random forest	Gradient boosted trees	Support vector machine
Corruption index (CI)	0.075	0.192	0.061	0.300
GDPG	0.069	0.079	0.051	0.004
INF	0.017	0.005	0.019	0.028
ROAA	0.010	0.014	0.010	0.009
ROAE	0.038	0.000	0.113	0.000
Size	0.014	0.004	0.093	0.162
Liquidity	0.039	0.006	0.120	0.001
MEf	0.420	0.210	0.384	0.068
IB	0.002	0.000	0.005	0.057
CR	0.032	0.005	0.087	0.000

4. CONCLUSION

This paper presents significant findings of research concerned with NPLs and corruption indexes as two important issues in banking institutions. Although corruption has a higher relationship to NPL generally beyond ML prediction models, the findings from this research found minimal effects to most of the selected ML algorithms. Therefore, further research is important to get insight into the issue with different ML learning algorithms. The DT, random forest, and gradient boosted trees are categorized as tree-based features selection mechanism, thus focusing on linear based ML might be the potential research to be conducted in the future.

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